

Path Integral Formulation of Free Propagator and Maximum Entropy Part III (Adding a Potential - the Oscillator Case)

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 26, 2021

In a previous note (Part II), we considered writing the energy of a classical free particle as $(X-Y)(X-Y)/TT$ ((1)) (X and Y are final and initial points and $T=T_f-T_i$). For a fixed velocity (with $Y=0$), X and T are directly linked. We argued, however, that one may consider changing X and Y independently so that a certain function, to be determined, is unchanged. (Note, dX and dT are linked in such a scheme.). Given that T is in the denominator in ((1)), its power in the denominator increases with derivation, while the power of X in the numerator decreases. Thus, the form $(X-Y)(X-Y)/T$ as an argument of a function, say $\exp\{-i [(X-Y)(X-Y)/T]\}$ which matches $\exp(iS_c)$ with S_c =classical action (used in the path integral type formulation for the oscillator (1)) will allow for T and X changes to cancel.

This yields a differential equation of the form of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation without $V(x)$. In this note, we investigate the effects of adding a quadratic potential to see that the oscillator case mimics that of the free particle closely. We argue that obtaining a differential equation for a free propagator, namely the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, allows for this equation to be generalized to a conservation of energy type equation with $\sum a(p)\exp(ipx)$ replacing $\exp(ipx)$ in a separable free particle solution. $\exp(-iEt)$ remains for both cases. The S_c approach based on $x(t) = XA(T_f-t)/A(T) + YA(t-T_i)/A(T)$, with $A(t)$ being a solution of Newton's equation, appears to apply to quadratic forms and seems to be related to frequencies with X playing the role of an amplitude.

exp(i Action) and the Free Propagator

In (1), an approach for calculating a path integral for an oscillator is given by suggesting the propagator is given by $Q(t)\exp(i S_c)$ where $S_c = \int dt L(t)$ where $L(t) = T-V$ is the Lagrangian. The position is $x(t) = XA(T_f-t)/U(T) + YA(t-T_f)/U(T)$ where $U(T)=A(T_f-T_i)$ where $A(t)$ is the solution of Newton's second law. From this, $dx(t)/dt$ yields the velocity. $x(t)$ and dx/dt may be inserted into the Lagrangian which is then integrated over time.

We argued in Part II, that this method may also be applied to the free propagator. In such a case: $A(T_f-t) = v(T_f-t)$ where v is the velocity. Setting $T_i=0$, one obtains:

$$L = (X-Y)(X-Y)/TT \quad \text{and} \quad S_c = (X-Y)(X-Y)/T \quad ((2))$$

S_c is then combined with an exponential to yield $\exp(i S_c)$ ((3)).

We argued, that one may obtain ((2)) directly without any knowledge of a Lagrangian if one treats X and T as independent variables, but allows for the changes of the two to "cancel". This is no longer classical physics, because $X(T)$ for $T_i=0$ $T=T_f$, $Y=0$ classically. One would not change X and T independently, even if one adds that extra rule that the change in T cancels the

second order change in X. Thus, we argued that a fluctuation approach results. Specifically, the differential equation that arises is:

$$i \frac{d}{dT} \exp(iSc) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i Sc) \quad ((4))$$

This is the time dependent Schrodinger equation. If one notices that ((2)) is ET, then ((4)) also becomes a conservation of energy equation for the free particle, but not with the propagator, rather with $\exp(-iEt + i px)$.

In the case of a potential, it seems one would generalize ((4)) to include the potential and generalize $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$ to $\exp(-iEt) W(x)$ such that $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$ yields that classical kinetic energy at x.

We have argued in a number of earlier notes that one may obtain the Schrodinger equation directly by assuming that $P(x)=\text{constant}$ on statistical grounds, but suggesting a single particle in a potential may have various different instantaneous momenta at different times. Thus, we described the system statistically as an ensemble of free particle conditional probabilities. Given that $P(x)=\text{constant}$, we wish to have a function of p,x with modulus 1. Furthermore, we desire that $\frac{d}{dx} P(p/x) = p P(p/x)$ i.e. the probability changes with p because it is based on p in the first place. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution for a single momentum and $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ for the ensemble. This may be inserted into the Schrodinger equation with $W(t)=\exp(-iEt)$ and $W(x)$ found i.e. the a(p)'s determined.

Interestingly, this approach seems to be linked to that of $\exp(i Sc)$ where Sc is the classical action. In this note, we wish to investigate this link, at least superficially, for the case of an oscillator and generalized oscillator.

Case of $\exp(iSc)$ and the Oscillator

For the free particle propagator, we consider $(1/2m) (X-Y)(X-Y)/T$ ((1)) as being a quantity which when taken in $\exp\{-i (1/2m) (X-Y)(X-Y)/T\}$ allows for $i \frac{d}{dT}$ to match $-1/2m \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dX}$. One requires $\exp(-i \text{function})$ i.e. a complex function in order to allow for the d/dT change to balance $-1/2m \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dX}$. We argue this is a special rule governing certain types of fluctuations in a classical system. This differential equation (time-dependent Schrodinger equation) has a second solution, namely the separable $\exp(-iEt - ipx)$. This suggests oscillatory behaviour with classical results appearing on average i.e. $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx)$.

One may readily see that ((1)) is KE Integral dt1 for a free particle, but it is not clear what one should do in the case of an added potential say $V(x)$ or even $V(x, dx/dt)$. The differential equation containing the fluctuation rule, however, may be readily generalized because in the $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ case, it is a conservation of energy equation namely:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) + V(x, dx/dt) W(x,t) \quad ((5))$$

In this note, we wish to investigate how ((5)) is linked to $\exp(i S_c)$ with S_c being the classical action. In the free particle case, $(X-Y)(X+Y)/T$ is the integral of kinetic energy over time. This does not directly generalize to a Lagrangian $T-V$. One may even ask why the potential should be included.

We begin with the idea that one writes $x(t) = XA(T_f-t)/U(T) + YC(t-T_i)/U(T)$ with $A(T_f-T_i) = U(T)$ where $A(t)$ is a solution of Newton's second law. We argue in a later section that this approach only works with quadratic type potentials e.g. $xx \, dx/dt$ etc because $A(t)$ is a periodic type of solution which holds irrespective of amplitude X . It appears that one considers different amplitudes of the same spring with different corresponding times of one given spring with a fixed period.

For the free particle, one has $(X-Y)(X+Y)/T$ and changes X and T independently in a function such that the changes balance (i.e. creates the time dependent Schrodinger equation). X and T change in the kinetic energy expression:

$$\int dt \{ XdA/dt/U + YdC/dt/U \} \{ XdA/dt/U + YdC/dt/U \} \quad ((6))$$

They also appear in the potential. If the potential contains a term quadratic term in x , then:

$$\{ XA/U + YC/U \} \{ XA/U + YC/U \} \quad ((7)) \text{ which has the same "form" in terms of } X \text{ and } Y \text{ as the kinetic energy term.}$$

Thus, it seems one deals with quadratic potentials.

If changes X and T independently in a function, such that the two changes cancel, then both the quadratic kinetic and potential energy pieces should be included. They, however, could be combined with a relative constant which may be positive or negative. If the constant is 1, that still leaves the question of using "energy" $T+V$ or the Lagrangian $T-V$. Using $T+V$, however, yields a constant for classical systems with constant energy. For example, for an oscillator, $T+V+E$, a constant. Thus, one uses a minus sign and the Lagrangian.

It may be further noted that if a solution to Newton's law is periodic (as in the oscillator case), KE contains v squared. If one writes $\sin(\omega t)$ (for the oscillator) as $1/2i (\exp(i\omega t) - \exp(-i\omega t))$, squaring yields a periodic function with double the frequency. The same idea holds for an xx term from a potential. In the oscillator case, integrating a periodic function with double the frequency i.e. 2ω yields a phase shifted function with double the frequency.

We first examine the case of a quantum oscillator and consider the quadratic XX pieces. Thus, we write $\exp(-i XX B(t)/[U(T)U(T)])$ where:

$$B(t) = 1/[UU] \int dt \{ XdA/dt(T_f-t)/U + YCdC(t-T_f)/dt/U \} \{ XdA/dt(T_f-t)/U + YCdC(t-T_f)/dt/U \} - k/2 \{ XA/U + YC/U \} \{ XA/U + YC/U \} \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Let } B(T) = Z(T)/[UU]$$

$$\{d/dT B\} (XX \text{ terms}) - .5kXX = -1/2m \{d/dX d/dX B\} (XX \text{ terms}) \quad ((9))$$

We obtain a real equation by allowing d/dX to operate each time on the argument $\exp(-i XX B/(UU))$. There is another term associated with $d/dX d/dX$, but this does produce XX which is the focus of differential equation in B to be determined.

What is interesting is that $U(T)$ plays the role of T in the free propagator. Thus:

$$id/dT (Z/[U]) = -2dU/dT / U B(T) + 1/[UU] dZ/dT \quad ((10))$$

We focus on the first term $-2dU/dT / U$.

The propagator for an oscillator is given in (1) as $Q(t) \exp\{-i .5mw [\cos wT/\sin wT (XX + YY) - 2xy/\sin 2wT] - 2XY/\sin wT\}$

$$U(T) = \sin(wT) \text{ and } B(T) = -.5mw \cos wT/\sin wT$$

(It may be noted that one might expect the coefficient $Z/[UU]$ for XX , but a U in the denominator has already canceled a U in the numerator before forming Z . In more complicated problems, this cancellation does not necessarily occur and one has UU in the denominator.)

Thus, $dU/dT / U = \text{constant } B(T)$. In other words, the first term in ((10)) is proportional to:

$$-2 B(T)B(T) \quad ((11))$$

This is exactly what is needed to balance the XX pieces of $d/dX d/dX$ which yield:

$$4 B(T)B(T) (1/2m)$$

The other terms of dB/dT must then cancel with $-.5 kxx$, which may be verified i.e. $d\cos wT/dt = -w\sin wT$ which cancels with the denominator $\sin wT$ leaving a constant term.

The point we wish to make is that part of the action of dB/dT namely $dU/dT / U (-2) B$ "matches" $2/m B(T)B(T)$ from $-1/2m d/dX d/dX$. Thus, one again has the $X-T$ change balance as in the free propagator case with a single derivative in T and a double in X , with only part of the $d/dX d/dX$ result in the potential case yielding an XX term. (This also holds in the free propagator case.) In other words, the motivating idea that one may vary X and T independently and balance the changes of a function holds.

Analysis of Simple Oscillator

In the above section, we argued that for $(X-Y)(X-Y)/TT * T$ for a free particle, one needs to write a corresponding similar kinetic energy term and also include XX terms from the oscillator potential. What happens to the T form which is no longer linear? For the free particle:

$(X-Y)(X-Y)/TT \int dt_1$ where $\int dt_1 = T$. Thus, $d/dT (TT) = a d/dT \int dt_1$.

In the oscillator case, TT is replaced with $U(T)U(T)$ and $\int dt_1$ with the integral in ((8)).

Thus, one obtains for the XX coefficient in $\exp(iSc)$: $XX Z(T) / [UU]$.

If $d/dT [UU] = \text{constant } Z(T)$, one has a similar relationship as in the free propagator case. This is exactly the scenario for the simple oscillator and so it is very similar to the free propagator.

That is, in the simple oscillator case:

$$d/dT (Z/U) = - dU/dT / U + dZ/dT / U = 1/2m BB + k/2$$

Thus, a possible solution is: $dZ/dt = \text{constant } U$. $Sc = XXZ(T)/ U(T)$ which is similar to the free propagator form $(X-Y)(X-Y)/T$ except that the linear T is replaced with $U(T)$.

Thus, we argue that the free propagator and oscillator are very similar. Physically, the oscillator has one frequency, but one considers changes to X , the amplitude, for such a system together with changes in T , the time particle arrives at an x point. Thus, one sees the nature of the fluctuation described by the Schrodinger equation. This fluctuation scheme is very similar in form to that of the free propagator

Generalized Quantum Oscillator

Next we consider the generalized quantum oscillator given in (2):

$$id/dt W = \sin t \sin t (-1) d/dx d/dx W + \cos t \cos t xx W + \sin(2t)x (-id/dxW) - i/2 \sin(2t) W \quad ((12))$$

The propagator is given in (3) as:

$$Q(t) \exp\{-i [XX (\sin t \sin ht - \cos t \cos ht) - YY \sin t \sin ht + \cos t \cos ht) \quad -2XY] / [M(T)] \} \quad ((13))$$

Where $M(T) = 2 \{ \sin t \cos ht + \cos t \sin ht \}$.

$$\text{Thus, } B(T) = (\sin t \sin ht - \cos t \cos ht) / [M(T)] \quad ((14))$$

(Note: $Q(t)$ may be found by considering the pure imaginary part of the Schrodinger equation.)

In this problem, quadratic terms in XX in $\exp(iSc)$ arise from $dx/dtdx/dt$, $\sin t \sin t$, $\cos t \cos t xx$ and $\sin(2t) x dx/dt$. The term $-V(x, dx/dt) \exp(iSc)$ (combined with $id/dT \exp(iSc)$) now yields two terms: $\cos T \cos T XX + XX \sin(2T) (-1/2) B$. Thus, one does not expect that B is of the form of $dN/dT / N$ (where $N(T)$ is some function) as in the case of a simple oscillator or the free propagator.

For the generalized case:

$$d/dT (Z/M) = -(dM/dT)/M B + (dZ/dT)/M = BB \sin T \sin T + \cos T \cos T + \sin(2T) (-1) B$$

$$= [\sin T B - \cos T] [\sin T B - \cos T] \quad ((15))$$

We use the form $B=Z/M$ because M is related to $U(T)U(T)$ where U is a solution of Newton's second law. In the case of the simple oscillator, there is a Newton's equation solution of the form $\sin(\omega t)$. Thus, one has $\exp(i\omega t)$ and $\exp(-i\omega t)$ type terms. Taking d/dt does not affect the frequency terms e.g. $d/dt \exp(-i\omega t) = -i\omega \exp(-i\omega t)$. Squaring doubles the frequency and creates constant terms. Integrating, like differentiation, does not change the frequency of a term. Thus, the simple oscillator problem may be solved without solving Newton's second law, but postulating $B(t) = Z(t)/[U(t)U(t)]$ and writing $Z(t)$ and $U(t)U(t)$ in terms of $\exp(i\omega t)$, $\exp(-i\omega t)$ and constant terms.

One may then solve the $id/dt B = 1/2m BB + .5k$ problem in terms of $\exp(i\omega t)$ type terms. We suggest that for the generalized oscillator problem, given the $\sin(t)\sin(t)$ coefficient of KE and $\cos(t) \cos(t)$ of xx , one may have $\exp(it-t)$, $\exp(it+t)$, $\exp(-it+t)$ and $\exp(-it-t)$ type terms in the solution. Linear combinations of these may be used for both $Z(t)$ and $M(t)$. The coefficients of each $\exp(it+t)$ type term could be complex, but $Z^*=X$ and $M^*=M$ reducing the number of unknowns. One may then try to solve ((15)) by treating each $\exp(-it+t)$ type term as independent. Of course, one may simply solve the differential equation ((15)), but it seems that the idea of frequencies (both real and imaginary) is present in the generalized oscillator problem as the solution ((13)) shows.

Thus, the generalized oscillator is not as straightforward as the free propagator or simple oscillator which mimic each other. Nevertheless, the idea of frequencies seems to still be present.

Potential of the Form $.5kxx + bxxx + cxxxx$ etc

We investigate whether the action approach may be applied to non-quadratic type potential terms. Consider a potential of the form $V(x) = .5kxx + bxxx + cxxxx$ etc and let $A(x)$ be a solution to Newton's second law.

According to the approach applied to the oscillator in (1): $x(t) = XA/U + YB/U$ where $U=A(T)$, $A(Tf-t)$ and $B=A(t-Tf)$.

$X d/dt dA/dt = -k X A(t)$ should hold if one collects coefficients of X , but this only works for quadratic type potentials because X is an amplitude not linked to the frequency. Thus, $A(t)$ is a general solution in time i.e. $\sin(\omega t)$ which does not give an explicit X value. This approach does not seem to hold in general.

If one uses a more general potential, one must collect coefficients of powers of X , but the LHS only contains a linear power, so there are problems. Thus, it seems that one may not apply this approach in general.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to extend the idea of a function whose d/dT derivative matches up to a constant factor its $-d/dX$ derivative introduced for a free particle to the case of a potential. The differential equation (i.e. the time-dependent Schrodinger equation) seems to be easily generalizable as it is linked to a conservation of energy equation. Given that X and T are changed independently, XX appears both in the classical kinetic energy and in quadratic i.e. xx terms of potential energy. (It may also appear in xdx/dt type terms in the potential energy.)

We argue that (quadratic) potential energy should be included with kinetic when trying to vary X and T to obtain a differential equation. A minus sign is used between KE and V otherwise one would obtain a constant for bound systems like an oscillator, so the Lagrangian is used. We find that the simple oscillator case mimics the free propagator closely as the $1/(TT)$ Integral $dt1 = T / (TT)$ and integral $dt1 KE - .5kx(t1)x(t1) / U(T)U(T)$ where U is an oscillator solution both have the property that: d/dT (denominator) = constant numerator.

We note that for given $x(t) = XA(T_f - t)/A(T) + YA(t - T_i)/A(T)$ for the oscillator, X plays the role of an amplitude. Thus, by changing X , one is considering different amplitudes i.e. fluctuations of the same spring and linking a change in amplitude to one in the time required to reach a particular x value. We argue this is the nature of the resulting time-dependent Schrodinger equation. The approach used for the oscillator mimics that of the free propagator closely and so we argue that the fluctuation ideas should also hold for the free propagator.

References

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